

Simulation of flow based optimal activation of reserves in regional balancing markets

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Regional balancing
Optimal activation of balancing reserves

ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to introduce an approach for enabling optimal activation of balancing energy resources within a regional balancing market. In order to take into account the constraints from the transmission network, the paper proposes a modified technique for optimal power flow calculation. This novel approach results in a more effective usage of transmission network capacities during reserve activation on a regional level compared to the conventional Common Merit Order List (CMOL) approach, which only considers the available cross-zonal transmission capacity (CZC) and disregards the physical power flows. The paper provides details on a procedure that includes simulation of electricity markets, as well as simulation on imbalances in the system. The methodology is used for evaluating the proposed approach on an IEEE test system comprising of three zones. The paper shows a significant reduction of balancing costs by implementation of regional balancing market it also investigates and shows the impact of the increased RES penetration to the amount of needed balancing energy in the system.

1. Introduction

Each imbalance between generation and consumption in power systems cause the system frequency to deviate. The system frequency should be maintained within predefined limits in order to ensure secure operation of the power system. Therefore, part of the generation and consumption in the system should be able to be adjusted with appropriate speed in order to maintain the power balance. This means that some of the generation capacity should be available to increase or decrease its power, but also the demand can participate in the balancing process by changing its power. These services are known as Frequency Support Services (FSS) and they consist of balancing reserve capacity (frequency regulation reserves) and balancing energy [1]. Since Transmission System Operators (TSOs) are responsible for frequency regulation and maintaining the security of the power systems, and they do not own generation or demand, a balancing capacity and energy markets are organised. The aim of these markets is to enable selection of the cheapest bids of FSS providers i.e. minimise balancing costs. Traditionally these markets are organised at national level.

At present, we face a major challenge in supporting the shift from

conventional electricity generation to renewable energy sources (RES) generation in power systems. The intermittent nature of RES generation poses significant challenges in the operation of power system, particularly regarding frequency regulation and stability. As a result, greater quantities of frequency regulation reserves should be deployed, and their activation rates should increase to ensure secure operation of the system and maintain sufficient levels of power quality and security of supply [2]. Therefore, this approach is associated with increased costs for balancing. This trend will cause the balancing costs to be comparable or even higher than the electricity costs in future.

The regional integration of balancing markets can improve the effectiveness and reduce the costs for frequency regulation. This is shown in the research papers [3–5] for Europe, for the electricity markets in general, and for the balancing capacity markets. The papers show a significant amount of savings by regional integration of markets. The regional integration of balancing markets will enable the cheapest and most effective FSS providers to be selected and used at regional level. Therefore, it is one of the main priorities of EU energy policy. The Load-Frequency Control and Reserves section of the System Operation Guidelines (SOGL) [6] and Electricity Balancing Guidelines (EBGL) [7]

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Fig. 1. Creation of CMOL.

network codes of the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E), tend to harmonize the processes of frequency regulation at continental level, create standardised FSS products, thus facilitating the regional and pan-European integration of balancing markets.

Along with the harmonisation of procedures and products, the regional integration of balancing markets should consider the limited capacity of transmission networks. Traditionally, the regional integration of balancing markets is done by creation of a Common Merit Order List (CMOL) by merging bids from FSS providers from multiple between Load Frequency Control (LFC) Areas that in most cases correspond to countries [7]. The network constraints are taken into account by limiting exchange of power between LFC Areas to the values of the so-called Cross Zonal Capacity (CZC). Many studies show the importance of taking into account the limited CZC when reserving and activating balancing capacity. For example, [8] analyses the impact of network constraints in cross-border reserve procurement. In [9], while presenting the options for organisation of markets for cross-border balancing of energy, the authors emphasise the need to take into account the transmission capacity between countries. While this method is straightforward and appropriate for cross-border balancing of a limited number of areas, it becomes more challenging when applied to multiple areas connected in a meshed network. This is due to the fact that physical power flows can differ significantly from commercial exchanges. This is especially true for regions with multiple small countries/zones that are connected in meshed transmission grid, as the region of Southeastern Europe [11,12].

The focus of this paper is to suggest a modified optimal power flow approach for optimal activation of frequency regulation reserves in regional balancing markets. Previous research, [13–16], has explored the optimal activation of reserves, but the modelling of the transmission network is based on simplified network models with a reduced number of nodes and elements. Namely in [13] the authors show the methodology for balancing energy market integration that is applied on a case study in Northern Europe. The methodology uses Net Transfer Capacity (NTC) value in order to take into account the limited transmission capacity of the network. In [14,15], the algorithm from [13] is extended to use inter-zonal Power Transfer Distribution Factor (PTDF). The paper [16] shows the benefits of common Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve market in the region of Southeastern Europe, and the available CZC is used as a limit in the process of bid selection. In contrast, in this paper the full transmission network is modelled. This approach is possible because the injected power at each node in the transmission network can be estimated with relatively low error by using measurements and state estimation in close to real time, when the balancing

market clearing is done. Additionally, the network topology information can be easily acquired from SCADA systems.

The accuracy of transmission network modelling is critical because it can influence the efficiency of its utilisation and improve system security, as demonstrated in [17]. In the paper [17], Security Constrained Optimal Power Flow (SCOPF) is used in order to determine the maximum amount of power that can be exchanged between zones in the process of cross border activation of balancing reserves. Another argument for improving the modelling accuracy in the process of regional balancing is that the transmission capacity of the network is primarily used by the trade in the wholesale electricity markets, with only the remaining capacity after the intraday market closure being utilized for exchange of balancing energy [18]. The proposed method considers the security constraints of the network according to the N-1 security criterion. As a result, a modified version of the SCOPF method is employed in the optimisation process itself, unlike in [17]. Direct current (DC) model for load flow calculation in transmission network is used in order to maintain the robustness of the optimisation process, which is usual in the application of optimisation in markets [19].

This paper is an extended version of [20], where a procedure for simulation of imbalances that enables easy application on the procedure for optimal activation of reserves on test or real systems is introduced and described in details. In the simulation of imbalances, the impact of the RES penetration on the needs for balancing energy is taken into account for wind power plants (WPPs). Similar procedures can be created for the other types of RES generation.

The second chapter of this paper outlines the principles of balancing reserve and energy markets. The third chapter introduces the optimisation method for optimal activation of reserves. The fourth chapter explains the simulation procedure used to test the proposed method on a standard test network. The fifth chapter shows the results of the method application to a test network composed of three areas from the IEEE Reliability Test System, which has 96 nodes. Lastly, the outcomes of the research are summarized in the conclusion.

2. Operation of the balancing reserve and energy markets

The markets for balancing reserve capacity and energy are the means of TSO to ensure readiness of generation capacities, demand or storage units to change is power input to the network (reserve capacity for frequency regulation), and to trade the energy for balancing in cases of power imbalances (balancing energy) [7].

Depending on factors like speed of activation and the timing of provision of balancing energy, there are various kinds of products for balancing capacity and energy. The SOGL network code outlines several

standardised products like Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR), Frequency Restoration Reserve (FRR), which can either be manual or automatic, and Replacement Reserve [6]. Markets for balancing reserve and energy are established for each of these standardised products. The balancing reserve markets operate on yearly, monthly, weekly, or daily basis, where the providers are chosen based on their offered prices, starting from the lowest, until the required reserve capacity is met. On the other hand, balancing energy markets operate in near real-time to ensure that the necessary quantities of balancing energy required to maintain equilibrium between energy generation and demand are obtained. After being selected in the balancing reserves market, the providers of balancing capacity are required to submit bids for balancing energy in the balancing energy market. However, in addition to them, other providers of balancing energy, known as "free energy bids," can also participate [21,22]. It is important to note that in these markets, capacity and energy are differentiated into upward regulation, which involves an increase in injected power, and downward regulation, which involves a decrease in injected power. Each participant in the market submits a bid with a specified quantity and price for the service they are providing.

The focus of this paper is on the market for balancing energy from automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR). The delivery period of aFRR balancing energy varies across European countries and can range from 15 to 30 min [7]. In this paper, the aFRR delivery period is set at 30 min. Therefore, the trading interval on the market for balancing energy from aFRR is considered also to be 30 min.

Increased competition in the balancing markets can be achieved through their regional integration. This involves the collection of balancing energy offers at the regional level, followed by the creation of a CMOL for activating the balancing energy providers also at the regional level. This list is then arranged in ascending order by price and the bids are activated based on the specific needs for balancing energy in each LFC Area. This approach only considers the value of CZC between LFC Areas and commercial exchanges between LFC Areas are limited in the corresponding direction to the remaining CZC value [7,11–16]. This procedure is done by so-called Activation Optimisation Function (Fig. 1).

Apart from the utilisation of CMOL in the regional balancing process, it is crucial to emphasise that the procedure for imbalance netting is also employed. It is common for two different LFC Areas to experience imbalances with different signs simultaneously, with one having a power surplus and the other a deficit. If this procedure is not implemented, it would require activation of downward regulation in the first LFC Area and upward frequency regulation in the second [7,11–16]. The activation of reserves can be reduced by implementing imbalance netting, which involves altering the exchange program between these two areas, with the LFC Area with a power surplus transferring it to the area with a power deficit. This procedure contributes significantly to reducing the activated balancing energy and associated costs.

3. Method for optimal activation of reserves for frequency regulation

The activation of balancing energy providers is based on the needs of each LFC area, aiming to achieve minimum costs while considering the limited transmission capacity of the network and technical constraints. Optimal utilisation of the transmission capacity is crucial to achieve minimum costs for balancing the system [7,11–16]. To address this, the proposed method formulates the reserve activation problem as an optimal power flow problem, using the DC approximation of the transmission network model to represent the entire network. Moreover, the method considers the N-1 security criterion and thus requires the problem to be formulated as a SCOPF [19].

The proposed method differs from the classic SCOPF in that it does not optimise the total generation, but instead focuses on optimising the change in injected power of the balancing service providers (generation,

storage, flexible consumption) compared to their position in the wholesale market. The goal is to achieve energy balance in the system for the defined time period (30 min for aFRR) with minimum costs, while also satisfying the network constraints. It is important to mention that this method will also enable elimination of congestions if they exist in the network before activation of the balancing service providers.

This problem is expressed as a constrained optimisation, with the objective function being the balancing costs. The balancing costs are calculated as the sum of payments to each activated provider of balancing energy for both upward and downward regulation. It is considered that each provider is paid a price according to its bid (pay-as-bid principle). Therefore, the objective function can be expressed as follows:

$$\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{g \in G} \left(\Delta P_{g,t}^{up} \cdot \Delta t_t \cdot C_{g,t}^{up} + \Delta P_{g,t}^{down} \cdot \Delta \vec{\theta}_{t_t} \cdot C_{g,t}^{down} \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

T – is a set of considered time intervals,

G – is a set of balancing energy providers,

$\Delta P_{g,t}^{up}$ – is the activated power for upward regulation of the provider g , in time interval t in MW,

$\Delta P_{g,t}^{down}$ – is the activated power for downward regulation of the provider g , in time interval t in MW,

$C_{g,t}^{up}$ – price of provided energy for upward regulation from provider g , in time interval t in €/MWh,

$C_{g,t}^{down}$ – price of provided energy for downward regulation from provider g , in time interval t in €/MWh,

Δt_t – duration of the time interval t (the interval of activation of the corresponding type of reserve – in this paper 30 min. for aFRR).

The amount of activated balancing energy is expressed in the Eq. (1), as a product of the activated power and the time interval for balancing.

In the example presented in this paper the balancing energy providers are generators only, but other types of providers, such as storage or flexible demand, can be incorporated easily. For the generators it is assumed that each unit provides a separate bid in the balancing energy market. The prices of the bids for upward regulation are set to equal the marginal costs of each unit $C_{g,t}^{up} = MC_g$. For downward regulation, the prices of bids are calculated as a difference between the wholesale market price (specifically, the Day Ahead Market (DAM) price) and the marginal costs of the generator unit. If this difference is negative, the price is set to zero, i.e. $C_{g,t}^{down} = \max(0, SP_t - MC_g)$ [14]. The optimisation includes an equality constraint for the balance of active power in the system:

$$\sum_{g \in G} \left(\Delta P_{g,t}^{up} - \Delta P_{g,t}^{down} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{Np} PP_{i,t} - \sum_{j=1}^{Ng} PG_{j,t} \quad (2)$$

where:

$PP_{i,t}$ – is the average power of the i th consumer for time interval t in MW,

Np – is the number of consumers in the system,

PG_j – is the average power of the j th generator for time interval t in MW.

The right-hand side of the Eq. (2) represents the power imbalance in the system, which is the difference between the total consumption and the total generation. This imbalance must be equal to the difference between the activated power for upward and downward regulation. When the transmission capacity of the network is insufficient, it may be necessary to activate upward regulation in some parts of the network and downward regulation in others. Although the Eq. (2) does not consider network losses, it is possible to incorporate them into the active power balance by calculating them based on power flows from the DC model.

Fig. 2. Simulation of the DAM.

Fig. 3. Types of simulated imbalances [6].

The activated power of balancing service providers (in this case generators) is restricted by their technical characteristics. Moreover, the maximum amount of activated power in both directions depends on the generator's output power before it is activated to provide balancing energy, as illustrated in the following equations:

$$\Delta P_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_{g,t}^{\max} - P_{g,t} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta P_{g,t}^{down} \leq P_{g,t} - P_{g,t}^{\min} \quad (4)$$

The constraints for active power flows through network branches should also be satisfied by the solution provided by the optimisation procedure.

Fig. 4. Example of ramping between LFC blocks [6].

These constraints are in place for the base case network scenario and also in operating conditions of the network with contingency of one network element (N-1 criterion):

$$|PGR_{i,k,t}| \leq PGR_{i,k}^{\max}, i = 1 \dots M, k = 1 \dots N_S \quad (5)$$

$PGR_{i,k,t}$ – active power flow in the branch i for scenario k , for time t ,
 $PGR_{i,k}^{\max}$ – maximum allowed active power flow in the branch i for scenario k ,

M – number of branches in the network,

N_S – number of scenarios (base case and scenarios with contingencies).

It is worth noting that the maximum allowed active power flow for branches $PGR_{i,k}^{\max}$ is determined based on the thermal current rating, assuming rated voltage and usual power factor for transmission. These values may be different for contingency scenarios and the base case scenario. The use of a linear DC transmission network model allows the

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the simulation procedure.

Fig. 6. IEEE RTS with 96 nodes and three zones [35].

Fig. 7. Values of NTC/CZC between price zones/LFC areas.

power flows through the network branches $PGR_{i,k,t}$ to be expressed as a linear combination of the activated power (optimisation variables), utilizing a reduced PTDF matrix [23]. Therefore the constraints and objective function of the optimisation are linear, and the problem is solved using linear programming [23,24].

The usage of the more precise Alternating Current (AC) transmission network model would turn the Eq. (5) into a set of non-linear constraints. Consequently, this may cause convergence issues, and the introduction of reactive powers and voltages as additional variables and constraints would further complicate the optimisation problem [24]. These are the main reasons for choosing the DC network model instead of the AC model in the proposed method for optimal activation of reserves, which is a step forward from current practice that only considers the network limitations by the CZC. Furthermore, the use of DC model for network modelling in market optimisation is a commonly accepted approach that can be seen in the literature [4,6–8,19,24].

Fig. 8. DAM price by areas, total demand and exchange between.

Fig. 9. Available reserves by areas.

4. Simulation procedure of optimal activation of reserves for frequency regulation

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method for optimal activation of reserves, a simulation procedure is developed. The procedure involves simulating the DAM and using the results to calculate the generation units' schedule at hourly intervals for a single day. The next step involves simulating power imbalances and calculating the required balancing energy needs from aFRR [25]. Finally, the method proposed in the previous section is applied to determine the optimal activation of reserves.

4.1. Simulation of the DAM

The DAM simulation relies on the costs for the generation units' operation. These costs follow a standard quadratic dependence from the output power, with known coefficients for the test network. In the simulation a piecewise linear approximation of the cost curve is used. Three characteristic points are used, such as the point of generators' minimum power, maximum power, and average power. From the linearized cost curve, three values for the marginal costs of the generator are calculated depending on the interval of generated power, and they are used as the prices of bids for the DAM. The simulation of an asymmetric centralized market is then conducted using these bids. The supply curve is formed by ordering bids from generators in ascending order, while the demand is represented as non-elastic with vertical line (as shown in Fig. 2). The bid with the minimum power for each generator is considered a block offer that must be accepted or rejected in its entirety. The RES generation is considered to have zero marginal costs and always is placed first in the supply curve.

The DAM simulation is carried out separately for each price zone that corresponds to the LFC area of the network. Subsequently, a market coupling is performed between these price zones, which requires knowledge of the CZC. The CZC is calculated based on network data. In the case of networks with three zones, a trilateral market coupling algorithm is utilized [34]. The market simulation determines the electricity price, exchange of power between price/LFC zones and the power output of each generator on an hourly basis.

4.2. Simulation of power imbalances

The simulation of power imbalances considers the following types of imbalances, that are identified in the SOGL [6]:

- Outages of generators or load.
- Continuous variations of load and generation – stochastic fast (noise) disturbance caused by fast variations of consumption and generation.
- Forecast errors of RES generation and load.

- Deterministic imbalances – a deterministic disturbance caused by the deviation between load and step-shaped schedules (mostly visible at the hour shift) and cause deterministic Frequency Deviations.

These imbalances are shown on Fig. 3.

4.2.1. Outages of generators or load

Monte Carlo Simulation is utilized in this research to model the power generation unit outages. The generation units can be in one of two states: normal operation or outage, and the transition from one state to the other is represented by a stationary Poisson random process [26]. This random process is defined by two constant parameters: the outage intensity λ , which is expressed in outages per year, and the repair intensity μ , which is the number of repairs that can be performed in a year. The duration of the generation unit's normal operation, denoted as T , is a random variable that follows an exponential distribution with a probability density given by:

$$f(t) = \lambda \cdot e^{-\lambda t} \quad (6)$$

While the duration of the generation unit's repair, denoted as τ , is also a random variable with the following probability density:

$$\phi(t) = \mu \cdot e^{-\mu t} \quad (7)$$

To simulate the operation of the generation units, arrays of random durations of normal operation and outage are generated using the probability distributions from Eqs. (6) and (7). Using these durations, the points in time when outages occur can be determined. The load outages are simulated at the same way as generation units' outages. The outage intensity λ in this case is significantly smaller.

The outages of generation units or load cause power imbalance, resulting in a deviation of the system frequency and activating the Frequency Containment Process. The process involves using balancing energy from FCR across the synchronous area to eliminate the power imbalance and stabilize the frequency. The process typically lasts up to 30 s and uses an insignificant amount of balancing energy [6,11]. To restore the frequency and the power interchange of the LFC block to their set value before the disturbance, the frequency restoration process is activated, freeing up the FCR. The energy from FRR is equivalent to the energy of the power imbalance caused by the outage, since the amount of energy provided by FCR is insignificant. If the imbalance persists, we can consider that the FCR is released by the replacement reserve after 30 min [6,11]. Therefore, during the simulation, the imbalance resulting from a generator or load outage is assumed to last for 30 min and is covered entirely by energy from aFRR (it is considered that manual FRR is not used).

4.2.2. Continuous variations of load and generation

Multiple random factors contribute to the continuous stochastic variation of load and generation, such as the frequent switching of load

Fig. 10. Simulated power imbalances on a minute level.

and the fluctuation of generation especially from RES. As a result, short-term imbalances can occur, both positive and negative [6]. These imbalances are modelled by introducing random changes in load and generation from RES at intervals of 1–5 min. The values of load and generation at these intervals are generated as random numbers with a normal probability distribution having an expected value equal to the actual load or generation (calculated by the market clearing as described in the previous subsection) and a given standard deviation [6].

4.2.3. Forecast errors of RES generation and load

The forecast for both load and generation depends on several factors, including the weather forecast and other observations, and is prone to errors. These errors can result in power imbalances. While conventional generation is relatively easy to plan and control, the forecast errors in renewable energy generation are often the leading cause of significant imbalances. This paper focuses on simulating imbalances caused by forecast errors in the generation from WPPs, as it is considered the one of the most substantial contributors to such imbalances.

The simulation process involves three distinct steps:

Fig. 11. Imbalances and balancing costs for each area – local balancing.

Fig. 12. Imbalances and balancing costs - regional balancing.

Table 1
Balancing energy and balancing costs.

Area	W_{up} (MWh)	W_{down} (MWh)	C (\$)
1	2416	2465	57,323
2	2799	2389	51,827
3	2566	2182	49,847
Total	7780	7035	158,997
Regional bal.	5917	5172	95,296
Difference	1863	1863	63,701
Difference (%)	24 %	26 %	40 %

- Simulation of the forecasted wind speed and determination of the forecasted generation from WPPs.
- Simulation of the wind speed forecast error and determination of the actual wind speed and generation from WPPs.
- Calculation of imbalances as the difference between the forecasted and actual generation.

It is important to note that this simulation procedure only captures the statistical nature of generation and is not intended for real generation forecasting from WPPs.

The wind speed is modelled as a random variable with a Weibull probability distribution [27–31]. The forecasted wind speed is simulated by generating random numbers with this distribution for each WPP at an hourly level. The probability density of the distribution is represented by the following equation:

$$f(v, c, k) = \frac{k}{c} \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^{k-1} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k}, v > 0 \quad (8)$$

where v is the wind speed, k is shape parameter, and c is average wind speed. The forecasted generation of each WPP, denoted as P_w , is determined by the forecasted wind speed v using the following equation [10]:

$$P_w = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq v < v_{ci} \\ a + b \cdot v^3 & v_{ci} \leq v < v_{ra} \\ P_{ra} & v_{ra} \leq v \leq v_{co} \\ 0 & v > v_{co} \end{cases}, a = \frac{P_{ra} \cdot v_{ci}^3}{v_{ci}^3 - v_{ra}^3}, b = \frac{P_{ra}}{v_{ra}^3 - v_{ci}^3} \quad (9)$$

where v_{ci} is the cut-in wind speed, v_{ra} is the rated wind speed, v_{co} is the cut-out wind speed, and P_{ra} is the WPP's rated power.

The error in predicting wind speed can be expressed as a Gaussian random variable, as noted in [32,33]. This means that by generating random numbers with a normal probability distribution, it is possible to simulate the actual wind speed. The expected value of the random numbers corresponds to the forecasted wind speed, while the standard deviation is typically 20 % [32,33]. Using Eq. (7), the actual power output of the wind power plant can be calculated based on the simulated actual wind speed. The power imbalance is then determined by comparing the predicted and actual power generation.

The forecast error for the system load is considered to be a random variable that follows a normal distribution. To simulate the actual load at each node on an hourly basis, random numbers with a normal distribution are generated, similar to how wind speed is simulated. The

Table 2
Needs for balancing energy.

P_{WPP} (MW)		Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		System	
		W_{up} (GWh)	W_{down} (GWh)						
0	Avg	112.7	112.9	112.2	112.6	110.1	109.8	250.3	250.7
	Stdev. (%)	1.03	1.01	1.13	1.12	1.19	1.28	0.83	0.85
200	Avg	113.3	113.1	125.3	125.0	106.7	106.6	250.5	249.9
	Stdev. (%)	1.19	1.21	1.16	1.25	1.19	1.15	0.92	0.91
400	Avg	113.3	113.1	155.4	153.9	108.3	108.3	270.5	268.9
	Stdev. (%)	1.14	1.14	1.41	1.44	1.21	1.17	1.05	1.05

expected value of the actual load is the forecasted load, and the standard deviation is considered to be 5 %.

4.2.4. Deterministic imbalances

Electricity markets operation and system operation planning processes in power systems are carried out on an hourly basis, taking into account only the average hourly values of load and generation. As a result, generation units are scheduled on an hourly level. However, the system load changes continuously over time, leading to deterministic power imbalances.

In the simulation, a continuous load curve is created by using cubic spline interpolation from the actual load values at each node, based on hourly data. The generation is represented by its scheduled power for most of the hour, but also the power ramping between hours is also considered. It is assumed that each generator uses its maximum ramping speed. The power ramping process begins before the end of each hour and the start time is such that the generator can complete half of the required power change at the end of the hour. The other half is done at the beginning of the next hour. The same principle is applied to the power interchange between the LFC blocks [6]. The agreed interchange for the next hour is achieved by making constant changes to the actual exchange in the last 5 min of the current hour and the first 5 min of the next hour, as shown in Fig. 4.

The simulated values of load and generation are used in the load flow calculations and ultimately in the optimisation. In reality, this data would be obtained from measurements and state estimation of the system.

4.3. Application of the optimisation procedure

As a final step, the optimisation procedure, explained in the preceding section, is implemented to determine the selection of balancing energy providers that will effectively eliminate each imbalance for a time period of 30 min.

The simulation procedure is presented by flowchart in Fig. 5.

The simulation requires input data for the generator units such as coefficients of a quadratic cost curve, minimum and maximum power, data for the network topology and parameters for calculation of DC load flow, and hourly load data i.e. forecasted load on an hourly base for each node.

The calculation of cross-border transmission capacity or NTC (which is equal to CZC) is done firstly based on the network data, at the same time simulation of the forecasted values of RES generation is done. The electricity market simulation is then performed using this data, resulting in the hourly schedules for both generation and load, electricity prices and scheduled power exchange between zones. Further on the simulation of all types of power imbalances is done, resulting with the needed quantities of balancing energy for each LFC zone on 30 min. intervals, and actual values of load and generation that differ compared to the forecasted ones. This data alongside the PTDF matrix of the network and DAM prices are used for performing the procedure for optimal activation of reserves. At the end the amount of energy for each provider and the balancing costs are known.

The presented simulation considers two alternatives. The first one assumes that each price zone/LFC area obtains the required balancing energy solely from providers within that area, without the existence of a regional balancing market. The second option involves simulating a regional balancing market where the imbalance netting occurs between LFC areas, and the activation of reserves provides balancing energy on a regional level, regardless of where the reserves are located. In the first case, Eq. (2) for the balance of active power is applied separately for each area. In contrast, for the second alternative, the balancing is carried out for the whole network/region, and Eq. (2) refers to the balance of the entire region.

The simulation procedure presented in this section of the paper is developed to enable application of the proposed optimisation procedure on a network model with known grid parameters and costs for generation. The optimisation of total generation is done by simulating the Day-Ahead Market as described in Section 4.1 and the purpose of this simulation is only to determine the scheduled power of generators in the system (unit commitment) and use it as starting point for simulating the imbalances of power in the system which is described in 4.2. The results of these two simulation procedures enable us to determine the operational state of the power system (realized power of generation units and load) and the amount of balancing energy that is needed to cover the imbalances. This data is input data for implementation of the optimisation of activation of balancing reserves and is not subject to optimisation. In reality this data would be extracted from SCADA system by using state estimation.

5. Application and results

5.1. Simulation of optimal activation of reserves in regional balancing markets

The previously presented model for optimal activation of reserves is applied on a test network IEEE Reliability Test System (RTS) 96 with three areas, that is shown on Fig. 6. Some data regarding the test network is modified in order to enable efficient application of the simulation procedure and representation of its characteristics.

Because in the test network all three areas are identical, in order to induce greater exchange of power and occurrence of congestions between the areas in some hours, the generators' costs for area 3 are increased by 30 %. Between the nodes 208 and 207, as well as 308 and 307 another parallel line identical to the existing is added so that the network satisfies N-1 criterion in the base case. In addition, in the node 222, four hydropower plants with installed power of 50 MW each, are replaced by four WPPs with installed power of 100 MW each ($v_{ci} = 4$ m/s, $v_{ra} = 12.5$ m/s, $v_{co} = 20$ m/s). The system's operation is evaluated for one week, which corresponds to the week with the highest load in the year, as per the data from IEEE RTS 96. Two scenarios are considered: in the first scenario, each area is balanced independently without any exchange of balancing energy between them, while in the second scenario, a regional balancing market and imbalance netting are established.

The calculated values of NTC are depicted on Fig 7. It is considered that each area keeps reserve (aFRR) of generation capacity of 400 MW, and this generation does not participate on the DAM. The calculated electricity prices from the simulation of the DAM for each of the three areas, (c (\$/MWh)), the total demand (P_{load} (MW)) and the scheduled exchange between areas (P_{ex} (MW)) are shown on Fig. 8. It can be noted that the price of electricity on the DAM for area 3 (marked in green) is greater than the prices in the other areas (marked with yellow line) at some hours because of congestions in the network. It can be noted that the area 3 imports power because its generation is the most expensive.

The available reserves for upward (positive) and downward regulation (negative) by areas ($Pres$ (MW)) are shown in Fig 9.

Fig. 10 shows the simulated power imbalances for each LFC area with granularity on one minute, as well as the sum of imbalances – that would be the imbalance if imbalance netting is applied in the region.

Fig. 11 shows the power imbalances in each of the three areas of the considered system at 30 min. time intervals and the costs for balancing in (\$/h). These results are for the scenario where each area is balanced independently and there is no regional balancing market.

Fig. 12 shows the imbalances and costs if regional balancing is applied.

The data for total activated balancing energy and the balancing costs for the whole week are summarised in Table 1.

From the table it can be seen that the application of imbalance netting and regional balancing leads to decrease of about a quarter of the needed balancing energy, in addition the balancing costs are decreased by 40 %. This reduction emphasises the significance of the regional integration of balancing markets, especially in future when the share of balancing costs in total costs for electricity supply is expected to rise due to the increased RES penetration.

5.2. Simulation of power imbalances depending on the level of RES penetration

In order to show how the amount of RES generation (from WPPs) influences the needs for balancing energy, additional simulations of imbalances were done, for scenarios with different installed capacity of WPPs, in area 2 of the previously described modified IEEE RTS 96. The simulations are done according to the procedure previously described in Section 4.2 which is based on the Monte Carlo Method. 100 Simulations with duration of one year are done and the results (average value of the needed balancing energy and its standard deviation) are presented in Table 2. The number of simulations is enough to get confidence interval of ± 0.5 %, with probability of 99.9 %.

The results show increased needs for balancing energy in area with the introduction of RES generation although the level of RES penetration is low. The simulation procedure parameters such as the error in forecast of wind speed (or RES generation) and its standard deviation can be adjusted so that real situations can be simulated.

6. Conclusion

The proposed approach for achieving optimal activation of reserves has two potential applications. Firstly, it could be utilized in the operation of regional balancing markets for bid selection. It is worth emphasizing that the approach takes into account the actual network topology and actual power generation and consumption received from state estimation systems, as well as the physical power flows and security constraints, rather than relying on simplified network models. Another benefit is that the method can assist with congestion management, particularly in the case of an integrated market for balancing energy and congestion management, since it accounts for power flow restrictions in all interconnected network lines [36–38]. Given the current popularity of new market designs, there is abundant opportunity for further research in this area.

The second application of the approach presented in this paper involves using the simulation procedure in conjunction with the optimal activation of reserves method. The simulation procedure could be used to analyse the potential benefits of future integration of balancing markets in terms of reducing balancing costs, as demonstrated in the last section of the paper.

A shortcoming of the presented research is a lack of presentation of clear results for the advantage of the proposed model for network modelling compared to the traditional limitation of cross border exchange according to values of CZC. This is hard to show this in terms of reduced costs and is related to the security of supply of the system and occurrence of congestions. Therefore, the future work in the research will involve applying the simulation procedure on a more complex actual network spanning multiple countries, namely that is the region of Southeastern Europe that are connected in a relatively well-developed meshed network as part of the synchronous interconnected system of

Continental Europe. This will allow us to thoroughly demonstrate the benefits of the enhanced precision introduced in our research when modelling transmission networks. Also, the future research should encompass the benefits in the process of congestion management in transmission networks.

The simulation outcomes featured in Section 5.1 of this paper illustrate the advantages of integrating electricity balancing markets at a regional level, leading to a substantial reduction in the expenses associated with balancing energy. These results provide a rationale for the ongoing initiatives within the European Union aimed at establishing platforms for the exchange of various balancing capacity and energy products, exemplified by projects like IGCC [39], PICASSO [40,41] MARI [42], TERRE [42].

The findings regarding the correlation between the degree of RES integration and the amount of power imbalances, shown in Section 5.2, indicate a growing demand for FSS providers in the future power grid. Consequently, we can anticipate an upward trajectory in the costs associated with balancing capacity and energy, which will constitute a more substantial portion of the overall electricity price. This emphasises the importance of development competitive markets for FSS on a continental/pan-European level.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petar Krstevski: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft. **Aleksandra Krkoleva Mateska:** Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Stefan Borozan:** Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Vasko Zdraveski:** Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Vesna Borozan:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision. **Rubin Taleski:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

This paper has been supported by the Horizon Europe project Transition to sustainable future through training and education (TRANSIT), grant agreement number 101075747. The paper reflects only the authors' views and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.epsr.2024.110146](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2024.110146).

References

- [1] J. Frunt, W.L. Kling, P.P.J. van den Bosch, Classification and quantification of reserve requirements for balancing, *Electric Power Syst. Res.* 80 (2010) 1528–1534, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2010.06.018>. Issue 12/December.
- [2] C. Huang, Q. Zhou, Y. Jia, W. Chen, Z. Jing, Y. Rong, D. Ruan, Research on European cross-region balancing market settlement method under high proportion of renewable energy, *Energy Rep.* 8 (2022) 1125–1136, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.02.083>. Supplement 4/ISSN 2352-4847.
- [3] D. Newbery, G. Strbac, I. Viehoff, The benefits of integrating European electricity markets, *Energy Policy* 94 (2016) 253–263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.03.047>.
- [4] M. Ihlemann, A. Stiphout, K. Poncelet, E. Delarue, Benefits of regional coordination of balancing capacity markets in future European electricity markets, *Appl. Energy* 314 (2022) 118874, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.118874>. ISSN 0306-2619.
- [5] K. Van den Bergh, R. Broder Hytowitz, K. Bruninx, E. Delarue, W. Dhaeseleer, B. F. Hobbs, Benefits of coordinating sizing, allocation and activation of reserves among market zones, *Electric Power Syst. Res.* 143 (2017) 140–148, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2016.10.012>.
- [6] ENTSO-E, “Network code on load-frequency control and reserves”, 28 June 2013. https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/load/.
- [7] Commission regulation (EU), on establishing a guideline on electricity balancing, final version, 16 March 2017 https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/.
- [8] K. Van den Bergh, K. Bruninx, E. Delarue, Cross-border reserve markets: network constraints in cross-border reserve procurement, *Energy Policy* 115 (2018) 193–205, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.10.053>. February.
- [9] G. Doorman, R. van der Veen, An analysis of design options for markets for cross-border balancing of electricity, *Util. Policy* 27 (2013) 39–48, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2013.09.004>.
- [10] ENTSO-E, Automatic frequency restoration reserve process implementation guide, 2021. https://eepublicdownloads.entsoe.eu/clean-documents/EDI/Library/ERRP/Automatic_Frequency_Restoration_Reserve_Process_v1.1.pdf.
- [11] EKC and IMP, “Final report: assessment of national balancing markets of beneficiary countries (Task 1)”, March 2019. https://www.energy-community.org/dam/jcr:e46d0613-35e0-43d0-9d2a-d98d430e315d/EKC_IMP_task4report_03_2019.pdf.
- [12] P. Krstevski, S. Borozan, A. Krkoleva Mateska, Electricity balancing markets in South East Europe — investigation of the level of development and regional integration, *Energy Rep.* 7 (2021) 7955–7966, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2021.05.082>.
- [13] Y. Gebrekiros, G. Doorman, Balancing energy market integration in Northern Europe — modeling and case study, in: 2014 IEEE PES General Meeting | Conference & Exposition, National Harbor, 2014, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PESGM.2014.6939477>. MD.
- [14] Y. Gebrekiros, G. Doorman, S. Jaehnert, H. Farahmand, Balancing energy market integration considering grid constraints, in: 2015 IEEE Eindhoven PowerTech, Eindhoven, 2015, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PTC.2015.7232410>.
- [15] Y. Gebrekiros, G. Doorman, S. Jaehnert, H. Farahmand, Reserve procurement and transmission capacity reservation in the Northern European power market, *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* 67 (2015) 546–559, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2014.12.042>.
- [16] J. Jeriha, M. Pečjak, E. Lakić, Common mFRR market in the SEE region, in: 2023 19th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), Lappeenranta, Finland, 2023, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM58374.2023.10161775>.
- [17] I. Avramiotis-Falireas, Haoyuan Qu, F. Abbaspourtorbati, M. Zima, The importance of accurate transmission system model for cross-border exchange of balancing energy, in: 2016 13th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), Porto, 2016, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM.2016.7521328>.
- [18] J.D. Sprey, T. Drees, D. vom Stein, A. Moser, Impact of balancing energy on network congestions, in: 2015 12th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), Lisbon, 2015, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM.2015.721>.
- [19] Zhifeng Qiu, G. Deconinck, R. Belmans, A literature survey of optimal power flow problems in the electricity market context, in: 2009 IEEE/PES Power Systems Conference and Exposition, Seattle, WA, 2009, pp. 1–6.
- [20] P. Krstevski, A.K. Mateska, R. Taleski, V. Borozan, Optimal activation of reserves in regional balancing markets, in: 13th Mediterranean Conference on Power Generation, Transmission, Distribution and Energy Conversion (MEDPOWER 2022), Hybrid Conference, Valletta, Malta, 2022, pp. 110–115, <https://doi.org/10.1049/icp.2022.3312>.
- [21] K. Poplavskaya, J. Lago, S. Strömer, L. de Vries, Making the most of short-term flexibility in the balancing market: opportunities and challenges of voluntary bids in the new balancing market design, *Energy Policy* 158 (2021) 112522, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112522>. ISSN 0301-4215.
- [22] A. Ivanova, J.L. Domínguez-García, C. Corchero, Frequency support markets and wind integration, *Energies* 14 (2021) 7450, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14217450>.
- [23] M. Todorovski, R. Ackovski, Reduction of PTDF matrix and its application in DC optimal power flow, *Int. Trans. Electr. Energy Syst.* 25 (2015) 1848–1859, <https://doi.org/10.1002/etep.1936>.
- [24] H. Wang, C.E. Murillo-Sanchez, R.D. Zimmerman, R.J. Thomas, On computational issues of market-based optimal power flow, *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* 22 (3) (2007) 1185–1193, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2007.901301>. Aug.
- [25] P. Krstevski, R. Taleski, A. Krkoleva Mateska, V. Borozan, “Simulation of Regional Electricity Balancing Markets”, 2nd South East European Regional CIGRE Conference, Kyiv 2018.
- [26] V.A. Levi, J.M. Nahman, D.P. Nedic, Security modeling for power system reliability evaluation, *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* 16 (1) (2001) 29–37, <https://doi.org/10.1109/59.910778>. Feb.
- [27] J. Lei, C. Wan, H. Chen, H. Ge, Z. Wang, Studies on algorithms of power system probabilistic production simulation considering wind farms, in: 2014 IEEE PES Asia-Pacific Power and Energy Engineering Conference (APPEEC), Hong Kong, 2014, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/APPEEC.2014.7066081>.

- [28] K. Zheng, J. Liu, S. Xin, J. Zhang, Simulation of wind power time series based on the MCMC method, in: 2015 5th International Conference on Electric Utility Deregulation and Restructuring and Power Technologies (DRPT), Changsha, 2015, pp. 187–191, <https://doi.org/10.1109/DRPT.2015.7432262>.
- [29] B.C. Gu, et al., Quasi-Monte Carlo simulation based economic dispatch with wind power integrated, in: 2016 IEEE Innovative Smart Grid Technologies - Asia (ISGT-Asia), Melbourne, VIC, 2016, pp. 264–269, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGT-Asia.2016.7796396>.
- [30] M. Turcik, I. Oleinikova, M. Kolcun, Wind power simulation in power system planning tasks, in: 2013 IEEE Grenoble Conference, Grenoble, 2013, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PTC.2013.6652225>.
- [31] C. Carrillo, J. Cidrás, E. Díaz-Dorado, A. Felipe Obando-Montaña, An approach to determine the Weibull parameters for wind energy analysis: the case of Galicia (Spain), *Energies* 7 (2014) 2676–2700, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en7042676>.
- [32] H. Bludszuweit, J.A. Dominguez-Navarro, A. Llombart, Statistical analysis of wind power forecast error, *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* 23 (3) (2008) 983–991, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2008.922526>. Aug.
- [33] B.M. Hodge, M. Milligan, Wind power forecasting error distributions over multiple timescales, in: 2011 IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting, San Diego, CA, 2011, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PES.2011.6039388>.
- [34] Trilateral market coupling, introduction. Available: https://www.epexspot.com/document/3827/060322_RefGroupsTLCAlgorithm.pdf.
- [35] P. Henneaux, D.S. Kirschen, Probabilistic security analysis of optimal transmission switching, *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* 31 (1) (2016) 508–517, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2015.2409152>. Jan.
- [36] J. Ponočko, A. Krkoleva Mateska, P. Krstevski, Cross-border DSM as a complement to storage and RES in congestion management markets, *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* 148 (2023) 108917, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2022.108917>. ISSN 0142-0615.
- [37] M. Pantoš, Market-based congestion management in electric power systems with exploitation of aggregators, *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* 121 (2020) 106101, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2020.106101>. ISSN 0142-0615.
- [38] M. Mahmoudian Esfahani, A. Sheikh, O.. Mohammed, Adaptive real-time congestion management in smart power systems using a real-time hybrid optimization algorithm, *Electric Power Syst. Res.* 150 (2017) 118–128, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2017.05.012>. ISSN 0378-7796.
- [39] International grid control cooperation (IGCC) https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/imbalance-netting/.
- [40] Platform for the international coordination of automated frequency restoration and stable system operation (PICASSO) https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/picasso/.
- [41] Manually activated reserves initiative (MARI) https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/mari/.
- [42] Trans European replacement reserves exchange (TERRE) https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/terre/.